

Grant Agreement No: 814958

AFC4Hydro

AFC4Hydro- On open data management

Description:

- As of May 2020 the AFC4Hydro opened for upload of data to a repository service provided by Zenodo (www.zenodo.org). This document will be stored on Zenodo and contains information of the AFC4Hydro project and a section from the Data Management Plan highlighting the ambition for sharing data in the public domain. The project's website, afc4hydro.eu, will contain updated information of data uploaded to Zenodo.

Date:	2020-05-27
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Work package:	WP5 – Communication and Dissemination
Lead beneficiary:	FDB
Dissemination level:	Public

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About AFC4Hydro

Active Flow Control system FOR improving HYDRaulic turbine performances at off-design Operation

See also <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/814958> and the project website www.afc4hydro.eu

Objective

The AFC4Hydro project addresses the development of a novel Active Flow Control (AFC) system for improving off-design operation of hydraulic turbines by mitigating deleterious flow phenomena during steady and transient operation including ramping of produced load. The main effect being increased reliability and flexibility, and reduced wear and tear. More specifically, this innovative and affordable AFC solution, allowing efficient utilization of existing hydraulic turbines, is planned to be validated at small scale in a model turbine and at large scale in two prototype turbines. A combination of technologies will be used to reduce the pressure and load fluctuations exerted on the machine induced by the draft tube flow using: (1) injection of pulsating momentum (IPM) with a specific frequency, amplitude and phase by means of actuators; (2) injection of continuous momentum (ICM) in the form of water jets with controlled speed and orientation directed against the swirling flow. A structural health monitoring (SHM) system will be developed to evaluate the effects of the injection systems in the structural response of the rotor, generator and bearings. These measurements will be used to optimise the machine performance. For that, a Controller will be programmed and tuned to reduce pressure fluctuations, structural loads and induced vibrations in real-time operation by continuously adjusting the injection systems. The final AFC system will also be tested against demanding transients like ramp up and ramp down. Special attention will be given to mitigate the powerful and dangerous flow instability provoked by the vortex rope breakdown. The success of the proposal will permit to extend the operating range of already existing turbines beyond the established safety limits, to increase their efficiency at off-design operation, to be able to face more frequent transients and to reduce the maintenance and operating costs.

Programme: H2020-EU.3.3.2. - Low-cost, low-carbon energy supply

Topic: LC-SC3-RES-11-2018 - Developing solutions to reduce the cost and increase performance of renewable technologies

Participants:

Institution	Web site	Primary contact
Polytechnical University of Barcelona (Barcelonatech)	www.upc.edu	Prof. Xavier Escaler (coordinator)
Technical University of Luleå	www.ltu.se	Prof. Michel Cervantes
Flow Design Bureau AS	www.fdb.no	Dr. Morten Kjeldsen
Vattenfall AB	www.vattenfall.se	Mr Carl-Maikel Högström
Statkraft	www.statkraft.com	Dr. Erik J. Wiborg
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Excerpt from Data Management Plan

Data from fundamental testing will as a rule be made public.

Data from testing of system/ objects containing assets with protected IPR, but that is of interest to be disclosed will either be:

- Truncated; i.e. parts of the data that reveals IPR is left out of the data-sets. Example: Results from hydroturbine runner simulation might be presented without revealing the geometry of the runner itself.
- Anonymized; e.g. relative values will be given. Example: Absolute hydraulic efficiency of hydroturbines cannot, in general, be shared. A common practice is to share such data by applying a relative value for efficiency.

The data will be made available using formats that are accessible with little effort, example:

- Geometry of objects. 3D Step files, which can be read by most CAD software.
- Data files: TDMS for most data, but ASCII for smaller data sets. TDMS is a binary data format that several software tools accept.

The AFC4Hydro web-site will (afc4hydro.eu) will contain information on how to access the database and how to read the data. Since the primary aim is to share data that can recreate results that AFC4Hydro disseminates, the authors/ institutions behind the different dissemination activities will keep data access information indefinitely.

Access to database will follow the rules of the repository that AFC4Hydro chooses. AFC4Hydro opt for choosing a repository/ data-base service that collect information of those accessing the data according to GDPR.